

THE EFFECT OF DIFFERENT SOIL TREATMENT ON SOIL AGROPHYSICAL PROPERTIES WHEN PLANTING POLY CROPS

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ABSTRACT

The scientific article presents the effect of various soil treatments on the agrophysical properties of the soil when growing melons on meadow loam soils of the Kashkadarya region. In field experiments, the improvement of the "physical clay" (<0.01) fractions of the soil, which characterize the state of fertility of medium loamy soils, changed depending on the depth of soil treatment. It was stated that when plowing was carried out to a depth of 30-35 cm, compared to the variants with surface treatment (chiseling 18-22 cm), the soil was treated by 1.7-2.1% in the 0-30 cm arable layer, by 1.7-1.9% in the 30-50 cm arable subsoil, and the amount of agronomically useful aggregates in the soil was increased by 8.5-8.8; 10.5-10.8%, respectively.

Keywords: Meadow gray soil, melon, basic soil cultivation, surface cultivation, plowing, chiseling, soil agrophysical properties, grain size, mechanical composition.

Enter. The mechanical composition of the soil is one of the main indicators that determine the most important fundamental properties and productivity of the soil, and first of all, it is of great agronomic importance. Soil properties such as density, porosity, water permeability, as well as water, air, and heat regimes are directly related to its mechanical composition.

According to the amount of soil mechanical elements, the properties of soil and rocks are not the same. The mechanical composition of soil and rocks is mainly

divided into sand, dust (soil) and muddy depths depending on its physical and physicochemical properties, and the mechanical composition of soil is based on the ratio of "physical sand" and "physical clay" fractions according to A.A. Kachinsky's perfected and easy-to-use classification. obtained [7; 331 p.].

It should be noted that the genetic nature of the soil, the property of combining physical clay (<0.01) fractions in them into structural aggregates, the amount, composition and exchange of cations and mineralogical composition of humus are important. The better these properties are in the soil, the more strongly the properties of clay particles are manifested in the condition of the same amount of physical clay. [5; 3-5 p.; 6; pp. 64-74].

Materials and methods. In 2023-2024, in order to carry out scientific research, field experiments were carried out in the conditions of non-saline soils of Qamashi district, Kashkadarya region, medium sandy loam with mechanical composition, seepage waters are located at a depth of 4-5 m (Figure 1).

The main (plowing 30-35 cm) and surface (scraping 18-22 cm) soil tillage depth was taken as the object of experiment.

The mechanical composition of the soil was determined according to the method of N.I. Savvinov at the beginning and at the end of the policy period, in each option, at two points, on average, 1.0 kg of soil samples were taken, brought

to a dry state, and passed through sieves with a diameter of 0.25-10 mm. [8; 440 pp.].

The obtained results and their analysis. "Physical clay", i.e. soil fractions with a diameter of less than 0.01 mm, is important in determining the mechanical composition of the soil, soil fertility, and affects a number of physicochemical processes in the soil, and the colloid particles in them are important in the formation of the soil structure. plays a key role.

When the mechanical composition of the soil was determined before conducting the field experiment in the experimental area, physical clay (<0.01 mm) fractions in the 0-30 cm arable layer were 39.1%, and in the 30-50 cm layer below the arable, it was 37.5%. , they contain 0.05-0.01 mm (coarse dust), 0.01-0.005 mm (medium dust), 0.005-0.001 mm (fine dust) and <0.001 mm (turbid) fractions 34.7; 8.7; 16.3 and 14.1%, respectively, in the 30-50 cm layer, 33.8; 7.4; It was observed that it was 16.7-13.04%.

Also, according to the mechanical composition, fractions of sand (1-0.05 mm) in a layer of 0-30 cm are 1-0.25 mm 3.4; 0.25-0.1 mm is 4.2% and 0.1-0.05 mm is 18.6, respectively 3.9 in the 30-50 cm layer in these fractions; 7.8 and 17.0% were considered. These fractions have high water permeability, do not have the property of elasticity, and are distinguished by their small moisture capacity and low structure.

In our field experiments, soil mechanical composition was determined at the end of the application period when the soil was treated in different ways, and when polyphysis was grown from seeds and seedlings. According to the obtained data, it was observed that in the options where the main soil tillage was carried out at a depth of 30-35 cm, the mechanical composition of the soil was significantly changed compared to the initial (2024) and the options where the surface was tilled (scratching 18-22 cm).

For example, the main tillage of the soil is carried out at 30-35 cm, and the

agronomic value of the physical clay fractions of the soil when grown from seeds and seedlings is 40.8-41.4% in the 0-30 cm layer, tillage 38.6-39.7% in the lower 30-50 cm layer, these indicators are on the surface of the soil (drawing 18-22 cm) 0-30 in processed and grown varieties from polys seeds and seedlings; 1.7-2.1% and 1.7-1.5% respectively in the 30-50 cm layer; according to the initial (2024) indicators, it was noted that it was 1.7-2.3 and 1.1-1.4% more.

Soil granularity (structure) is an important agronomic property that determines its fertility and crop yield. A number of physical, physical and mechanical properties of the soil, water-air, heat and nutrient regime, as well as microbiological processes occurring in the soil, directly depend on its granularity [1; pp. 102-109; 3; pp. 97-101; 4; pp. 44-47].

In the production of granular soil, the activities of animals living in humus soil, which is produced from the remains of plant roots, especially the role of earthworms, are of particular importance, they pass organic and mineral particles and increase soil granularity. . Also, crop rotation and tillage (such as plowing, harrowing, cultivation, fertilizing) play a role in the formation of aggregates [10; pp. 11907–11916; 11; pp. 50-53; 14; 124 pp.].

In this case, early cultivation is the correct implementation of the soil cultivation system suitable for the soil conditions in each region. In our experiments, in different methods of soil treatment, i.e., the main treatment is the effect of plowing, the depth of plowing on the surface of the soil, on the state of aggregates in the layers of the field soils where poly crops are grown, and changes in the macroaggregate components were noted.

In the field experiment field in the first year (2023), after harvesting the previous crop of winter wheat, before plowing, when the soil structural condition was determined, macroaggregates larger than 10 mm in the 0-30 cm layer of the soil were 28.2%, 10 - up to 0.25 mm - 66.3%, soil particles smaller than 0.25 mm - 5.5% 32.6, respectively, in the 30-50 cm layer; It was found to be 63.1 and 4.3%. In

the options where the main tillage of the soil before planting polys seeds is carried out by plowing 30-35 cm, the amount of agronomically valuable aggregates of 10-0.25 mm in the average years (2023-2024) in the 0-30 cm layer is 71, 7% on the surface of the soil (chiseling-18-22 cm) in treated options 69.4% of the polys seedling on the soil before planting 71.4% in the variants with the main plowing 30-35 cm, 69.4% in the variants with surface (scraping 18-22 cm) plowing, useful aggregates in the variants with a plowing depth of 30-35 cm it was noted that the amount will increase.

In the variants grown from seeds and seedlings of polys, the differences in the soil macrostructure composition of soil treatments were almost not noticeable (0.2-0.3%), the main changes were in the main soil (plowing 30-35 cm) and surface (drawing 18- 22 cm) differed when processed. In our experiments (before planting from seeds and seedlings), in the options where the main soil tillage was plowed 30-35 cm, compared to the initial (2023) granularity before plowing, agronomically useful 10-0.25 mm aggregates 0-30 cm 5.4-5.1% in the layer, by 2.3-2.6% compared to the variants treated with soil surface treatment before planting, It was found that it increased by 6.3-6.1% and 1.7-1.9% in the 0-50 cm layer, respectively.

When the crops were analyzed at the end of the growing season, changes in soil grain size were observed as a result of the influence of atmospheric precipitation, irrigation water, air temperature and relative humidity. For example, agronomically valuable aggregates of 10-0.25 mm plowing 30-35 cm treated polys seed and seedling options planted in 0-30 cm layer on average 69.6-69.7%, 30 Layers (0- 30; 0-30; 30-50 cm) and 2.8-2.4% and 2.8-2.5% decrease in granularity was noted.

The amount of agronomically useful aggregates of 10-0.25 mm in layers (0-30; 30-50 cm) at the end of the 3-year period of the experiment in the options treated with soil surface (drawing 18-22 cm) is 62.2-61, 9; It was found that it decreased by 58.8-58.4% or by 8.5-8.8% and 10.5-10.8%, respectively, compared to the

options where the main plowing of the soil was carried out at 30-35 cm.

Conclusions. The analysis of our field experiments shows that according to the mechanical composition of the grassland gray soils of the experimental area, the improvement of the "physical clay" (<0.01) fractions of the soil, which characterizes the fertility and structural condition of the medium sandy soil, is due to different soil treatments. according to the depth the main plowing 30-35 cm depth tillage soil surface (scratching 18-22 cm) compared to treated options 1.7-2.1% in 0-30 cm arable layer, 1.7-1 in 30-50 cm sub-arable layer .9%, the amount of agronomically useful aggregates of the soil is 8.5-8.8, respectively; By ensuring that it is 10.5-10.8% higher, the physical (soil density, porosity), water-physical (water permeability, moisture capacity, moisture) and physico-mechanical (stickiness, viscosity, elasticity) properties, it provides an opportunity to improve the granularity, which is convenient and valuable for the growth, development and formation of root crops.

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